

BOTTLENECK OF KINDERGARTEN TEACHERS IN MOTHER TONGUE-BASED MULTILINGUAL EDUCATION IN LAMBAYONG MUNICIPALITY

Joan D. Castillo

Zeneben Integrated School, Division of Sultan Kudarat, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the bottleneck of kindergarten teachers in mother tongue-based multilingual education in Lambayong municipality for the school year 2023-2024 among eight kindergarten teachers. It employed a phenomenological study using thematic analysis in processing the responses of the participants.

On the issue of the bottleneck of kindergarten teachers using their Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in the Maguindanaoan area, the following themes are generated based on the responses of the teacher participants of the study, limited learning resources, lack of teacher training/seminars, and communication barriers.

On the coping mechanism of teachers that they are native to the language of the community that they are assigned the following themes were generated based on the statement of the teacher participants of the study, incorporating culturally relevant content and translations of unfamiliar words.

Interestingly, the policy formulation, be crafted in the deployment of kindergarten teachers not speakers of their mother tongue strengthening localization.

Keywords: *Bottleneck, Kindergarten Teachers, Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education, Coping Mechanism, Lambayong*

INTRODUCTION

Language choice for the medium of instruction has also been linked to measures of economic and social inequality. A recent study of the countries of Africa by Coyne (2015) indicates that using the former colonial languages as the medium of instruction has a direct relationship to inequality.

In Southeast Asia, a rising number of educational programs encourages a mother tongue approach in teaching and learning different core areas. Cambodia, Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, Timor Leste and Vietnam are among the countries in the region which adhere to the emerging language-in-education policy (UNESCO, 2011). In line with this, the programs are being utilized at the community level with support from international non-governmental agencies. While the use of non-dominant languages in education is allowed in each of these countries, the Philippines is the single country to institute a national policy requiring their inclusion in the early grades.

Research increasingly shows that play expedites a variety of social, cognitive, motor, and linguistic improvements (Eberle 2011; Fisher et al. 2011). Social play allows children to become more creative and more adept at explaining meaning verbally, more successful at manipulating different symbol systems, and more confident when experimenting with new activities (Bjorklund and Gardiner 2011).

The Philippines as a multilingual country has a different scene setting when it comes to the institutionalization of a national policy requiring mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE) in the primary school years (Burton, 2013). About such implementation, many studies have long supported the use of the mother tongue as the language of instruction. However, these researches have primarily been conducted in the community rather than national settings.

Furthermore, despite the complications faced, the MTB-MLE has been perpetually implemented over the last six years. Department of Education representatives further argued that employing the mother tongue as the language of instruction in the country is integral in the education sector. Consequently, enforcing the implementation of the use of the mother tongue as the language of instruction (DepEd Order No. 74, series of 2009).

However, since its implementation, it has been facing several issues and criticisms. For instance, the challenges on how to implement it such that it is aligned with the desired mother-tongue approach (Eslit, 2014) and the challenge implied by Lartec (2014) to the Department of Education to initiate a mechanism wherein the teachers' innovative strategies and problems are assessed, monitored, and evaluated. The interpretation and implementation in the classroom define the success of the enactment of the policy; what happens on the ground level will contribute either directly or indirectly to the successful implementation of the language policy. How could this materialize if the teacher in the Maguindanao area is a non-speaker of their Mother Tongue?

Thus, this study will be conceptualized to explore the bottlenecks of non-Maguindanao teachers teaching in the Maguindanaon area.

Research Questions

It is on this premise that this study was anchored on the bottleneck of Kindergarten Teachers teaching MBT-MLE and they are not speakers of the MTB of the community.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions.

1. What is the bottleneck of kindergarten teachers using Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in the Maguindanaon area?
2. What are their coping mechanisms to have an interactive and engaging teaching and learning process using their mother tongue?
3. What policy formulation may be crafted in the deployment of kindergarten teachers not speakers of their mother tongue?

METHODOLOGY

The study uses qualitative research, particularly phenomenology research design that interprets the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations.

A Semi-structured guide survey questionnaire was used to collect the necessary information and responses from the participants of the study.

The participants of the study were eight (8) kindergarten teachers assigned in the Maguindanaon area who are not speakers of the dialect of Maguindanaon. The following inclusion criteria were followed to select the participants of the study; a. must be a regular or permanent teacher, b. teaching kindergarten, and c. not speaking the dialect of the community.

RESULTS

On the issue of the bottleneck of kindergarten teachers using their Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in the Maguindanaon area, the following themes are generated based on the responses of the teacher participants of the study, limited learning resources, lack of teacher training/seminars, and communication barriers.

On the coping mechanism of teachers that they are native to the language of the community that they are assigned the following themes were generated based on the statement of the teacher participants of the study, incorporating culturally relevant content and translations of unfamiliar words.

Interestingly, the policy formulation, be crafted in the deployment of kindergarten teachers not speakers of their mother tongue strengthening localization.

DISCUSSION

On the issue of the bottleneck of kindergarten teachers using their Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in the Maguindanaoan area, the following themes are generated based on the responses of the teacher participants of the study, limited learning resources, lack of teacher training/seminars, and communication barriers.

Teacher participants of the study shared their thoughts about this and;

“The potential bottleneck in using mother tongue as a medium of instruction in Maguindanaoan area could be limited resources such as lack of standardized materials or curriculum tailored to the specific linguistic and cultural context”. **Participant 1 Female, Cebuana.**

“Limited educational resources in the local language, the challenge in adapting standardized curriculum materialize”. **Participant 4 Female, Ilocana**

On the coping mechanism of teachers that they are native to the language of the community that they are assigned the following themes were generated based on the statement of the teacher participants of the study, incorporating culturally relevant content and translations of unfamiliar words.

With this thought teacher respondents shared their coping mechanism to have a meaningful teaching and learning process, as they shared;

“Incorporate culturally relevant content, utilize interactive activities, encourage peer collaboration, and leverage visual aids to create an engaging and interactive teaching and learning process using their mother tongue”. **Participant, female, Cebuana**

“I would incorporate interactive games and activities. Visual aids and props, storytelling, community involvement, incorporate local context and encourage peer interaction”. **Participant 3, female, Ilocana**

“I employ a variety of teaching strategies, integrate multimedia materials, promote candid conversation, and offer authentic examples that are pertinent to the cultural background. Establishing a welcoming and encouraging atmosphere to encourage learners to express themselves in their mother tongue”. **Participant 4, female, Ilocana**

Interestingly, the policy formulation, be crafted in the deployment of kindergarten teachers not speakers of their mother tongue strengthening localization.

The teacher participants shared their thoughts on the policy formulation, be crafted in the deployment of kindergarten teachers not speakers of their mother tongue in the Department of Education the theme generated was **strengthening localization**, as they shared;

“Established language proficiency requirements, offer language training programs and promote cultural sensitivity to ensure effective deployment of kindergarten teachers in areas where they are not native speakers of the mother tongue”. **Participant 1, female, Cebuana**

“The policy in the deployment of kinder teacher could be based on language preferences of the teacher. Also, the teacher assigned in an area could be speaker also of the community’s mother-tongue”. **Participant 2, female, Ilocana**

“The deployment of kinder teacher should have set of criteria and the main standard should be culturally language proficient and trained in MTB-MLE pedagogy”. **Participant, female, Ilocana**

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The following themes were generated, limited learning resources, lack of teacher training/seminars, and communication barriers. Incorporating culturally relevant content and translations of unfamiliar words, and strengthening localization on the deployment of teachers.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented; The school may craft a school learning action cell that deals with continuous professional development. goes. The school may strengthen the implementation of a Learning Partnership Program that seasoned teachers may coach or mentor the neophyte teachers. The Department of Education may look into the deployment of kindergarten teachers especially in the context of inclusivity. This study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture quantitatively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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